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**RIGHTS OF NATURE FRAMEWORK
AN APPROACH TOWARDS PROMOTING ECOSYSTEM
PROTECTION AND RESTORATION IN THE PHILIPPINES**

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13 May 2023

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This Special Project titled: “**RIGHTS OF NATURE FRAMEWORK: An Approach Towards Promoting Ecosystem Protection and Restoration in the Philippines**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Malaya M. Sadiwa

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Abstract

This paper aims to present and introduce the Rights of Nature concept as a growing global framework movement that seeks to protect the environment by recognizing that nature, particularly ecosystems, like humans, have intrinsic rights to live.

The Rights of Nature framework acknowledges that ecosystems and natural communities are not mere assets subject to ownership; instead, they are living entities with an inherent and unassailable right to thrive and endure. Its mission is to promote the preservation and revitalization of ecosystems.

As of 2022, 24 countries, including Colombia, New Zealand, Bangladesh, Australia, India, seven Tribal Nations in the U.S. and Canada, and over 60 U.S. cities and counties, have introduced laws recognizing nature's rights. In various parts of the world, local and national courts have granted ecosystems the status of living beings and, in some cases, personhood. New laws are continuously being developed to regulate and protect the natural environment. These laws have changed how we view ecosystems and natural communities, giving them rights that can be enforced by people, governments, and communities working to benefit nature.

In 2018, the Rights of Nature have been adopted in the Philippines. It is now a growing movement in the Philippines, and they are also pushing for a bill called the Rights of Nature Act 2022 that aims to protect the country's ecosystems by giving legal personhood to nature.

I. INTRODUCTION

As environmental harm and destruction continues to occur worldwide, the United Nations has raised an alert that we are edging closer to a "significant global catastrophe." As a result, there is a mounting movement and acknowledgment that humans need to change their connection with nature and environment.

The Rights of Nature framework is a concept that calls for a paradigm shift and eco-centric view that benefits Nature not only for the human species but for Nature itself, in recognition of her intrinsic value.

The Rights of Nature (RoN) framework suggests that ecosystems should have their own rights, like people and businesses do. This means ecosystems and species would have legal permission to survive, grow, and renew. This approach aims to give nature a voice and recognize the basic rights of all things, ecosystems, and parts of the Earth to be alive, flourish, and change.

The Philippines embraced the Rights of Nature in 2018. It is now a growing movement in the Philippines and they are also pushing for a Rights of Nature Act to protect the country's ecosystems. Recognized and made into a flagship program by a non-government organization called PMPI Inc (Philippine Misereor Partnership Incorporated) and NASSA/Caritas, it now rallies people that nature should be given legal rights through a paradigm shift, an eco-centric economic, legal and governance framework and system that will promote nature's kinship with humans (I Am Nature), promote sustainable or Sapat Lifestyle, circular economy and regeneration of ecosystems.

With the continuous threat to our country's ecosystems, just like the recent Mindoro oil spill, deforestation in Sierra Madre, destruction of the Alusiis River in

Zambales, mining in Sibuyan Island, Tampuan and other parts in the country, this research paper will also present how the Rights of Nature Ph bill, if passed, can prevent destructions like these.

The Rights of Nature movement is getting more popular as both the lower and upper House of Representatives are backing it. It is also being supported by many organizations now as a strong solution to address the climate crisis.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In this chapter, related literature, studies, research articles, and conceptual frameworks were reviewed, gathered and studied to gain a thorough understanding of the concept, definition of terms and subject matter. And in recent years, due to the response and rising concerns of people, communities and nations about environmental degradation and the impact of human activities on natural ecosystems, the notion of "rights of nature" has become more noticeable. Several articles and research works have also focused about the activities of the Rights of Nature movement in the Philippines. And this includes some studies about the Philippine bill that aims to give nature legal rights just like people have.

Here are some of the relevant literature and articles that discussed the subject:

1. *"Wild Law: A Manifesto for Earth Justice"* by Cormac Cullinan (2003).

This book suggests that legal rights should be given to natural communities and ecosystems, treating them like legal persons. It introduces the idea of wild law, which aligns human laws with earth's legal philosophy, discussing that nature should have rights just like people. The book also proposes a new legal framework that recognizes nature's value and the strong connection between humans and the natural world.

2. *"Philippine bill seeks to grant nature the same legal rights as humans"* by Leilani Chavez (2019).

An article on Mongabay news portal discussed how the proposed Rights of Nature bill could change how we view environmental protection. The current Philippine laws about the environment mostly focus on people, not the environment the RON bill,

things are different; it aims to legally protect nature as its own entity with its own rights and legal representation.

2. *"The Philippines may be the next nation to grant rights to nature"* by Zach Fitzner (2019).

Another article published that articulates how the Rights of Nature bill can change the anthropocentric view of humans, and the belief that he is on top of the apex. The Rights of Nature is deeply rooted in faith. In May 2015, Pope Francis released *Laudato Si'*, urging us to protect the Earth. He emphasized the severe impact of the ecological crisis on people and the planet, calling for urgent action on climate change. He stressed that the climate is a shared resource. [12] The article also suggests the Philippines may grant legal rights to nature. In the West, nature – which includes animals, plants, rivers, mountains, ecosystems haven been always seen as separate from human. Embracing and recognizing the Rights of Nature means acknowledging the need for ecological change and restoring human's acceptance that nature and humans are one.

4. *"The Rights of Nature: A Legal Revolution That Could Save the World"* by David R. Boyd (2017).

An insightful and life-transforming literature, the book makes us see how cultures and laws are changing to provide a new and powerful approach to protect the planet and the species. It reminds us that we do not own the planet and other species have the same equal and legal right to the planet. And if humans begin understanding this legal and philosophical foundations which is the rights of nature movement, then this is a good approach to address the environmental crises facing the world today.

The book also shared how lawyers from California to New York are fighting the

legal rights and advocating to end the practice of captivity of intelligent animals like chimpanzees and killer whales. In Hawaii and India, judges have recognized that endangered species—from birds to lions—have the legal right to exist. The book is inspiring and groundbreaking as it showed the growing movement to recognize the rights of ecosystems—rivers, forests and mountains. It also reminds humans of their responsibility to other life forms and nature.

5. *"The Community Environmental Legal Defense Fund: Rights of Nature"* by CELDF.

As part of the development of the paper, it is important to trace the historical evolution of the Rights of Nature movement. By understanding its origin, how it grew, and the situation of the nations that adapted it, we may be able to craft the strategies for the Rights of Movement in our country. The information provided in the website detailed the history and timeline of the Rights of nature evolution. It acknowledges that the Rights of Nature concept has its origins in traditional indigenous wisdom and represents an evolution in Western law and philosophy.

6. *"Earth Jurisprudence: Private Property and the Environment"* by Peter D. Burdon (2011).

This book explores the intersection of property law and environmental law and advocates for a legal system that recognizes the inherent rights of nature and places limits on human ownership and exploitation of natural resources. The text offers examples like Bolivia's constitutional recognition of earth rights, the Whanganui River declaration in New Zealand, and a court granting rights to a captive Argentinian orangutan. This illustrates the legal system's growing recognition of nature's rights and how it can be a potential in protecting ecosystems.

7. *"Earth Jurisprudence: Private Property and the Environment"* by Peter D. *"Environmental*

Laws Impeded by Lack of Enforcement, First-ever Global Assessment Find” by IISD (2019).

This highlights the worldwide problem of weak law enforcement, which exacerbates existing environmental challenges. It also cites incidents involving environmental defenders wherein the subjects experienced harassment, unjust detainment and murder. 908 individuals were killed from years 2002 and 2013 and they were forest rangers, government inspectors, and activists. In 2017, 197 environmental defenders lost their lives. Hence, this paper also emphasizes the crucial role of political will in ensuring effective environmental laws. The report also reveals the reasons why problems like pollution, declining biodiversity, and climate change continue to persist despite the proliferation of environmental laws.

8. *“The Community Environmental Legal Defense Fund: Rights of Nature Timeline”* An article in CELDF (2018).

This journal also provides a review on the history and timeline of the Rights of Nature evolution. It recognizes that the idea of Rights of Nature can also be traced in traditional indigenous knowledge. It also traces the historical evolution of the Rights of Nature movement and by understanding its origin, how it grew, and how nations adapted it, we may be able to craft the strategies for the Rights of Movement in our country.

9. *“Catholic environmentalists call on the Philippine Congress to recognize the rights of nature.”* (2023).

According to a recent survey by Social Weather Stations (SWS), 93% have personally experienced the effects of climate change over the past three years and this can be traced to the collapsing ecosystem. Unless immediate and strategic actions are taken to reduce or halt climate change and avoid potentially irreversible

impacts

In summary, the literature on the rights of nature presented how the movement is seen as the immediate and best solution to counter the irreversible damages we have done to the planet and save the remaining ecosystems we have. It stresses the importance of an ethical, holistic approach to environmental management, acknowledging nature's inherent value and human's connection to the natural world. The Philippines has advanced its environmental laws, gaining recognition as a leader among developing nations by the end of the 20th century. For instance, Republic Act No. 9512, the National Environmental Awareness and Education Act of 2008, aims to raise national awareness about the vital role of natural resources in economic growth and the significance of environmental conservation for sustainable national development. Yet despite many green laws, environmental damage continues to persist in the country.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The statement of the study is how can the Rights of Nature Framework be an approach towards promoting ecosystem protection and restoration in the Philippines.

With the Philippines experiencing the severe consequences of climate change and the climate crisis, a significant portion of its 111 million people residing in urban areas, particularly in coastal regions are now vulnerable to the rising sea levels and affected by erratic and intense rainfall. Elevated temperatures are now affecting food security and population safety. Thus, there is an immediate need to safeguard the environment and its ecosystems. It is now only a matter of action for various stakeholders, including communities, scientists, government officials, and some legislators to act upon the situation. [1].

There is now a need for a new and stronger environmental law that is holistic in protecting ecosystem protection and restoration to adapt to changing global conditions. And a powerful legal way is to provide nature legal personhood and give it the same intrinsic right to life accorded to human beings.

3.1 Background of the Study

The Philippines recognized as one of the world's ecological hotspots, hosting numerous endangered and threatened species, is a top global priority for conservation efforts. Home to various ecosystems, the biodiversity in the Philippines has sustenance, water, energy resources, pharmaceuticals, biomass fuels, carbon storage, climate control, crop pollination, cultural and spiritual significance, and ecotourism value. The forests in the Philippines also yield both timber and non-timber

products, with annual net benefits of \$100 million and in which around 30 percent of the population, including 12 to 15 million indigenous communities, lives in upland regions where most of the forests are found [2].

There are more than 13 general environmental laws and policies in the Philippines now [3]. And though the Philippines has one of the best environmental laws created to protect our rich biodiversity, the laws are not implemented properly and it does not take the protection of nature or the ecosystem as a whole.

The Rights of Nature calls for a fundamental shift to recognize the need to live in harmony with nature. And this can be achieved if nature is granted legal protection and high societal value, acknowledging and giving it rights the same as human rights.

3.2 Defining nature and ecosystems in the Study

Rather than focusing on individual species or specific locations, the concept of the Rights of Nature is rooted in the protection of complete ecosystems. The definition of an ecosystem includes both biotic (living) and abiotic (non-living) elements that operate as an integrated system. Biotic elements houses all living organisms, while abiotic elements consist of non-living components. Additionally, an ecosystem represents an ecological community composed of diverse populations of organisms that coexist within a specific habitat. [4].

As an archipelago, the Philippines' geographical configuration is rich in topography. From coastal wetlands to upland watershed regions, the nation's terrain exhibits remarkable diversity marked by distinctive attributes. The unique landscapes resulted to a rich array of ecosystems – each with a variety of species that have adjusted, persevered, and thrived in specific areas for their survival.

a particular area for existence. Species endemic to the country has been

related to In the Philippines, a range of ecosystems exists, including terrestrial, freshwater, brackish/estuarine, and saltwater/marine ecosystems. But its alarming to not that these ecosystems are now constantly threatened by human actions like illegal logging, forest deterioration, mining, illegal fishing, wildlife trafficking, and more. These varied ecosystems have vital roles in the food chains and food webs and nurturing life in our nation. [5].

As each nation must follow the SDG goals, the Rights of Nature reflects the SDG Goal #15, which centers on protecting, restoring, and promoting the sustainable use of land and forests, fighting desertification, reversing land degradation, and stopping biodiversity loss. And by adopting the sustainable development practices, it provides a guide for the nations to safeguard their precious natural resources for the present and future generations.

The term "nature" includes living plants and animals, geological processes, weather, matter, and energy. It can also mean the "natural environment," like wilderness with wild animals, forests, and untouched places. [6].

In addition, natural ecosystems develop over time through a series of evolutionary experiments without human involvement while artificial ecosystems rely on human intervention for upkeep.

3.3 Significance of the Study

With UN nations also now agreeing to a 'historic' deal to protect a third of the world's biodiversity and protect a third of the planet for nature by 2030, several countries are now beginning a peace pact with nature and resetting their relationship with the natural world [7]. Recognizing the Rights of Nature framework is imperative to address the environmental degradation happening on the planet now.

PMPI Inc (Philippine Misereor Partnership Incorporated) together with NASSA/Caritas Philippines launched the Rights of Nature (RoN) campaign in the Philippines last 2018 and started to lobby for a national law that recognizes nature as a legal entity vested with rights. An NGO with a church/faith-based group working with 230 partner people organizations in the country, PMPI is at the forefront of the Rights of Nature movement in the Philippines, advocating for the passage of the Rights of Nature Act.

The Rights of Nature Ph b seeks to give nature the legal right to protect itself at a constitutional level. It created and is now lobbying for the Rights of Nature Ph bill that seeks to legislate to recognize the protection of the entire ecosystem and not just one part or entity. And by recognizing it to have an intrinsic right the same as human rights, it can now legally represent itself to be accorded its natural right to life.

Last July 7,2022, Senator Risa Hontiveros, filed the Senate Bill No.143, also known as the RIGHTS OF NATURE ACT OF 2022, a proposed legislation that acknowledges the rights of natural ecosystems, populations, and processes and outlines mechanisms for their protection and enforcement is currently receiving support from three congressmen.[8].

If passed as a bill, this legislation will affirm nature's rights and give communities the authority to resist government actions that allow destructive development. It will also empower communities and stakeholders to advocate for the rights of endangered ecosystems.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study will help define the importance and significance of the Rights of Nature framework in the Philippines and how it can be a powerful legal, non- anthropocentric and holistic tool to protect and restore the ecosystems – through restoration and protection of water and land from destruction to ensure the survival and safety of natural resources for the environment, IPs and people; and help address the global biodiversity loss and the effects of climate change.

Specific Objectives

4.1 The study seeks to explore how the Rights of Nature framework has shaped the development of The Rights of Nature Act in the Philippines, also referred to as the RoN Ph bill. This proposed law seeks to acknowledge natural ecosystems, populations, and processes as legal entities possessing specific inherent and unalienable rights, which includes the right to exist, regenerate, and undergo restoration. It also serves to provide guidance and direction to legislators and government authorities in the development of policies and the establishment of local ordinances for environmental safeguarding.

4.2 The study also intends to assess the potential of the Rights of Nature framework in the Philippines to safeguard the ecosystem, mitigate the severe consequences of climate change on the environment, and promote a shift towards more responsible and accountable conduct by governments and businesses in their dealings with the environment.

4.3 The study also aims to see if the framework and bill can indeed help restore and regenerate nature also. And analyze the relationship between Human Rights and to Rights of Nature – its co-existence and interdependence. At present, the country is

suffering the impacts of climate change but despite this, lawmakers continue to grant permits to mine and destroy the forests, marine ecosystems and mountains.

V. RATIONALE

The Rights of Nature framework seeks that if we want to sustain life and all living and natural resources in our planet, then there should be a paradigm shift to an eco-centric perspective towards recognizing intrinsic rights of nature and promoting ecosystem protection and restoration.

The Rights of Nature framework is the aggressive and creative solution to address the gaps in the existing environmental laws in our country and in every nation. It treats the protection of the ecosystem as a whole and secures its sustainability of life and resources for all future generations to come.

With the climate crisis worsening, as per the World Health Organization, it is estimated that climate change is set to lead to approximately 250,000 extra annual deaths from 2030 to 2050. These casualties will be linked to malnutrition, malaria, diarrhea, and heat stress. [9].

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

Since the Rights of Nature framework is a new and radical approach to address the environment degradation and climate crisis, the scope covers the study of the movement in countries only that have recognized the framework. Most of the data gathered are from news and articles of countries, towns, municipalities that have adopted the framework and passed the rights of nature bill to address the environment issue in their area. The events, legal discussions and random interviews of participants in the Rights of Nature also provided key insights for the study.

The limitations of the framework include that of being a concept and a call for the legal system to have paradigm shift. Here in the Philippines, the Rights of Nature movement is gaining traction in various civil society organizations, environmentalists and communities but it has failed to engage the legal sector and the press/media also. Hence, there is little support for the concept as of the time being.

The data gathered here are also dependent on the respondent's personal experience in their environment. There are no data to show how the Rights of nature have protected an ecosystem because it is still being lobbied. But the growing ecocentric attitude of some legal personalities are encouraging in pushing the recognition of the framework.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The description of the study area includes the origin, background and historical evolution of the Rights of Nature movement. By understanding its origin, how it grew, and the situation of the nations that adapted it, we may be able to craft the strategies for the Rights of Nature movement in our country.

The study also covers the definition of nature and ecosystem, that will help support the discussion on the importance of ecosystem management and conservation.

7.1 Origin

The Rights of Nature is a new legal paradigm that started in western culture. The idea argues that nature holds inalienable rights, and that vital parts of Nature — a river or watershed or ecosystem — shall be granted personhood in the court of law and be provided with legal standing to defend itself [10].

The Rights of Nature movement can be traced back to 1972, when the Southern California Law Review published law professor Christopher Stone's described how under the existing structure of law, nature was considered right-less, having no legally recognized rights to defend and enforce. It presented a new legal paradigm in western culture. With law professor Christopher Stone's seminal article, "Should trees have standing – toward legal rights for natural objects." Stone described how under the existing structure of law, nature was considered right-less, having no legally recognized rights to defend and enforce. It was picked up by Professor Roderick Nash, who published *The Rights of Nature: A History of*

Environmental Ethics [11].

It steadily opened the minds of environmentalists and academicians from 1989 to 2001. The concept was then strengthened by Thomas Berry who published *The Origin, Differentiation and Role of Rights* in which he described how all members of the Earth community possess inherent rights. Academician Professor Thomas Berry researched and wrote publications that detailed a history of environmental ethics and the Role of Rights where all members of the Earth community possess inherent rights [12].

Figure 1. The origin of the rights of nature.

Note. From communityrights.us. n.d.

The Rights of Nature concept was picked up by several countries. Ecuador became the first country in the world to recognize the Rights of Nature in its national constitution. In 2011, the first Rights of Nature court decision was issued in the Vilcabamba River case in Ecuador, upholding the Rights of Nature constitutional

provisions [13].

In 2003, South African attorney Cormac Cullinan wrote a manifesto for Earth Justice and Thomas Berry opened a new front on the Rights of Nature – adding a significant spiritual and moral element to the legal and historic discussion [14].

The first laws establishing legal structures that recognized the Rights of Nature were adopted by local municipalities in the United States in 2006. Tamaqua Borough, Schuylkill County, Pennsylvania, was the first community to enact the Rights of Nature. Since then, more than three dozen communities have adopted such laws. In November 2010, the City of Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, became the first major municipality in the United States to recognize Rights of Nature. In September 2008, Ecuador became the first country in the world to recognize Rights of Nature in its constitution. Bolivia has also established Rights of Nature laws [15].

In 2018, RoN was adapted by PMPI Inc as its flagship program to address the needs of the environment and lobbied the RoN bill in the House of Representatives.

As of 2022, nature's rights laws exist in 24 countries - including Colombia, New Zealand, Bangladesh, Australia, India, seven Tribal Nations in the U.S. and Canada, plus over 60 cities and counties throughout the United States. A number of ecosystems around the world have been declared living entities by local or federal courts, many of them also granted personhood, and laws are being codified to manage, conserve, and protect the natural environment.

7.2 Global Countries recognizing Rights of Nature

Ecuador made history by becoming the first country in the world to ratify a

constitution amended to include nature's rights. In Article 71 of the redrafted constitution states that Pachamama (mother earth) not only has the right to exist but also to have its “maintenance and regeneration of its lifecycles, structures, functions, and evolutionary processes” respected. In 2011, a lawsuit against the Provincial Government of Loja, was filed on behalf of the Vilcabamba River, which had suffered from debris buildup from a road-widening project. The court ruled in favor of the river, marking the first time Pachamama's rights were legal.

In 2017, New Zealand made news for granting the Whanganui River the legal rights of a human being. Colombia’s Constitutional court also approved legal rights for the Atrato River in 2017, near the Panama border, citing the precedent set in New Zealand. The court's decision was a major win for the river and its ecosystems, which had been threatened by mining in the area. Another river legally declared a living entity in 2017 - the Yarra River in Victoria, Australia. It was a landmark decision not only for advancing the country's natural rights but also for Australia's Aboriginal population, notably the Wurundjeri people of the Yarra River Valley. While in the US, Pennsylvania passed an ordinance recognizing the rights of the area's ecosystems, which were being degraded by sewage sludge being dumped on farmland. In 2019, the Supreme Court proclaimed all the rivers in Bangladesh to be alive and entitled to legal rights. In northern India, it ruled that the Ganges and Yumana rivers deserved legal rights and protections [15.1].

7.3 Early environment cases in the PH

In 1993, a group of children, including those of renowned environmental activist Antonio Oposa, brought this lawsuit in conjunction with the Philippine

Ecological Network, Inc. (a non-profit organization) to stop the destruction of the fast-disappearing rain forests in their country.

The plaintiff children based their claims in the 1987 Constitution of the Philippines, which recognizes the right of people to a “balanced and healthful ecology” and the right to “self-preservation and self-perpetuation” (see Section 16, Article II). Oposa also raised the idea of “intergenerational equity” before the court, which is the idea that natural resources belong to people of all ages and that if adults were to harvest all of a country's resources, they would be stealing from their children, their children's children, and all future generations.

The Supreme Court ruled in favor of the children, and made several groundbreaking and powerful statements, finding: the right to a clean environment, to exist from the land, and to provide for future generations are fundamental.

There is an intergenerational responsibility to maintain a clean environment, meaning each generation has a responsibility to the next to preserve that environment, and children may sue to enforce that right on behalf of both their generation and future generations.

The Philippine Constitution requires that the government “protect and promote the health of the people and instill health consciousness among them.” (See Section 15, Article II).

The *Factoran or Minors Oposa*, is a landmark decision of the Supreme Court of the Philippines recognizing the doctrine of intergenerational responsibility on the environment in the Philippine legal system. The case is a contributor to the development of international environmental law [15.2].

Though this event happened almost two (2) decades before the Rights of Nature framework was brought and introduced to the Philippines, nevertheless it

shows that there is an intrinsic desire and awareness of the Filipino people to recognize the rights of the environment to be sustained and restored for future generations.

7.4 The evolution of the Rights of Nature PH

The Rights of Nature PH was adapted by PMPI Inc as its flagship program to address the needs of the environment. In 2018, PMPI Inc started to promote the Rights of Nature to its 230 partners and to the House of Representatives.

Today, the Rights of Nature PH is a growing civil society movement advocating for a change in human relationships with nature. It creates a platform to coordinate actions to protect people and nature.

The main objective of the Rights of Nature is to have a shift in perspective – from a human-centered and utility-driven human relationship with nature to a perspective that recognizes human and nature's shared common and deeply intertwined evolutionary history.

From an *anthropocentric view*, the movement aims to shift it to an *ecocentric view* so that a national law that recognizes nature as a legal entity vested with rights can now protect the continuous depletion of forests, and rivers from becoming biologically dead, and wildlife being poached endlessly. It also challenges the idea that the Earth's living systems are properties and objects primarily for humanity's use and that they are resources that are infinite. It also seeks to end large-scale industrial extraction and pollution [16].

From an *ecocentric view*, the Rights of Nature aims to protect the environment for all creatures. It inherently follows the ecocentric paradigm, where most, if not all,

current environmental protection measures, are anthropocentric.

Ecocentrism finds inherent (intrinsic) value in all of nature. It takes a much wider view of the world than does anthropocentrism, which sees individual humans and the human species as more valuable than all other organisms.

Ecocentrism is also the key to sustainable natural resources because all environmental judgments based on it have a wider scope than human-centric environmental ethics and provides more long-term and future effects toward the natural environment [16.2].

7.5 The creation of the Rights of Nature Act of 2022

Last July 7, 2022, Senator Risa Hontiveros filed Senate Bill No. 143 or the "Rights of Nature Act of 2022". The bill was also filed by the following congressmen in the House of Representatives: Hon. Arnan Panaligan of District 1, Oriental Mindoro – filed last Feb. 14, 2023, Albay 2nd District Representative Joey Salceda - filed last February 9 and Cong. Edgar M. Chatto, Bohol Representative, 1st District – filed last February 20, 2023.

Infanta Quezon also made a historical mark by filing the 1st rights of nature ordinance in the country last November 29, 2022. Filed and championed by Vice-Mayor L.A. Ruanto of Infanta Quezon, the Rights of Nature ordinance establishes the Agos River as a Protected Area in the Municipality of Infanta, Quezon recognizing its RIGHTS and appropriating funds thereof.

The proposed legislation recognizes the rights of nature to exist, to the maintenance of nature's vital cycles and functions, and to the conditions necessary for nature's renewal and restoration. It will also enable the defense of the

environment in court – not only for the benefit of the people, but for the sake of nature itself.

Further, the legislation ensures that the Government of Philippines “shall take all necessary action to protect and enforce” the rights of nature. Importantly, the bills empower the Filipino people themselves to act on behalf of nature and protects their individual right to defend nature from being targeted by “Strategic Lawsuits against Public Participation” (SLAPP) [17].

The Rights of Nature bill will recognize the rights of our diverse ecosystems. This bill will ensure the protection and restoration of nature.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this paper is through the qualitative method of content analysis from the printed publication resources such as news and feature articles, journals and related literature. Pie charts and bar graphs were also used to present data. The qualitative method of an interview through an unstructured format, where key informants, lawyers, local stakeholders, and IPs were interviewed, their collected data through recorded field notes and observation were also used.

This SWOT analysis aims to evaluate the efficacy of the framework and lobbying efforts, as well as measure the impact on community behavior, stakeholder actions, and policy recommendations. The analysis draws upon information obtained from databases, digital resources, manuscript writing, as well as direct interviews and gathered data.

8.1 Strength and advantage of the RoN framework and bill

The rights of ecosystems and natural communities are enforceable independently of the rights of people who use them. That means that people within a community could step “into the shoes” of a mountain, stream, or forest ecosystem, and advocate for the rights of those natural communities. It calls for a system of jurisprudence in which those ecosystems are actually “seen” in court. Damages are assessed according to the costs of restoring the ecosystem to its pre damaged state.

Communities that have enacted Rights of Nature laws are empowered to reject governmental actions permitting unwanted and damaging development which would violate these rights. Rights of Nature laws enable people, communities, and

ecosystems themselves to defend and enforce such rights. Without the ability to do so, those ecosystems would be destroyed. Although people have been talking about “sustainable development” for decades, very little has been done to change the structure of law to actually achieve that goal.

They disallow activities that would interfere with the functioning of natural systems that support human and natural life [20]. Laws recognizing the Rights of Nature finally codify the concept of sustainable development.

Earth Law or earth jurisprudence, including Rights of Nature, could also help strengthen and evolve the current legal protections of nature in the Philippines. Earth Law is an ethical framework that recognizes nature's right to exist, thrive and evolve - enabling nature to defend these rights in court, just like corporations can [21].

The RoN also calls for a paradigm shift into the anthropocentric thinking of man that he owns the natural resources and it is for his disposal. The RoN teaches men to respect life which is in teachings of the bible, humility, and kindness to all living entities in the earth.

The Rights of Nature is also founded on the ecocentric view which holds that nature has intrinsic rights and as such should be protected for its own self. [22]

One of the strengths of the Rights of Nature is the recognition of nature as a legal entity. This means that nature has legal rights and protections, similar to how a human or corporation has legal rights.

The Rights of Nature framework also promotes conservation and preservation of natural resources by considering the impact of human actions on the environment. And it aligns with Indigenous knowledge and traditions that view nature as a living entity that must be respected and protected.

And lastly, RoN encourages sustainable development and practices that have

long-term impact of development on the environment.

8.2 Challenges and weaknesses of the RoN framework and bill

Like anything new, the Rights of Nature concept is sometimes met with skepticism and rejection mostly by lawmakers saying that the environment should not be the topmost priority but should still be poverty, hunger and even sickness.

The campaign is not yet picked by the media and still needs to be lobbied to as many stakeholders for it to be recognized and gain support. This is also caused by limited budget to mainstream its campaign.

Some view the RoN movement as not timely with the current political climate, poverty-related social and environmental problems and the country's low score in enforcing the law.

One of the major weaknesses of the Rights of Nature framework also is the lack of legal precedence. While some countries have recognized the Rights of Nature, there is still a long way to go before it becomes a globally accepted legal concept.

The implementation of the Rights of Nature may also be challenged since it requires a significant shift in legal and regulatory frameworks, as well as changes in societal attitudes towards nature and the environment. A conflict with existing legal frameworks that prioritize economic growth and development over environmental protection may also arise. And because of the lack of clarity on the scope of rights, it may lead to confusion and uncertainty in legal proceedings.

8.3 Opportunities for the environment

Many nations have expanded their body of legal rights to recognize a human right to a healthy environment. This includes a number of European nations, including Spain, France, Portugal, Greece, and Finland. The recognition of such rights should mean that the highest legal protection is implemented and enforced and the human right to a healthy environment can only be achieved by securing the highest protections for the natural environment – by recognizing in law the right of the environment itself to be healthy and thrive [23].

The Rights of Nature, once recognized by the court, will give weight to the harm inflicted on it and decide how to address and balance the situation. The RoN movement is seen to unite all green minded stakeholders to make one bold and strong call for policy reforms in the country. Plus, the RoN is supported by the Pope through the *Laudato Si* which reminds people to respect all life forms and that these living forms have a right to life and the universe.

8.4 Threats and struggles of the RoN framework and bill

Money and power are usually used to buy the law. The Rights of Nature framework may face opposition from industries that prioritize economic growth over environmental protection, as it may limit their ability to exploit natural resources. It is seen as a threat by others hence works against its implementation.

The lack of political will to implement the Rights of Nature framework may also pose a significant threat to its success, as it requires significant changes in legal and regulatory frameworks. And cultural differences and barriers in societies with no view of nature as a legal entity or place a high value on environmental protection.

The lack of sufficient enforcement mechanisms for the Rights of Nature

framework may also pose a threat to its effectiveness, as it may not have the necessary teeth to prevent environmental harm. And the killing of environmental defenders and indigenous peoples, who are allies of the Rights of Nature has not stopped in places around the world. As they continue to fight against climate change and biodiversity loss, activists together with communities play a crucial role as our first line of defense against ecological collapse.

In the Philippines, our environmental defenders are always in danger and constant threat, as they work to prevent our natural resources from being destroyed forever. Since our country is naturally blessed with the rich mineral deposit in our land, the Philippines ranks top five countries for mineral resources [24].

However, the Philippines remains the deadliest country in Asia for land and environmental defenders, with 270 of them killed in the last decade, according to an international non-government organization. Over 80% of the killings in the country over the past decade were connected to protests by defenders against company operations related to mining industry, followed by agribusiness sector [25].

IX. RESULTS

The Rights of Nature can be traced back in 1972, but it was only in 2018 that the Philippines recognized the concept and potential of the idea. Four years after, the Rights of Nature framework pushed for a bill to be passed called the Rights of Nature Act of 2022 which was championed in the House of Representatives. The movement is gaining traction as many are now awakened with the situation in our environment.

According to global forest watch, in 2021, it lost 37.7kha of natural forest, equivalent to 22.5Mt of CO₂ emissions. Explore interactive charts and maps that summarize key statistics about forests in Philippines [26].

The condition of Philippine coral reefs has also been in constant and rapid decline. A recent study shows that 90% of our reefs are in poor to fair categories and none in excellent state. The dismal condition of our reefs is further exacerbated by destruction of marine habitats including dump-and-fill projects, destructive fishing practices, pollution, climate change and other anthropogenic pressures. When properly managed, a square kilometer of tropical reef yields 15 tons of seafood a year – a resource critical to the planet's estimated 6 million reef fishers and their families. Nearly one million of those fishers reside in the Philippines alone [27].

The Philippines is one of the richest countries blessed with minerals and according to the Philippine Statistics Authority, a third of the country's total land area of 30 million hectares contained high deposits of gold, nickel, copper, and chromite, among others. As of February 2022, there were 55 operating metallic mining sites in the country [28]. These mining sites continuously destroy the environment, pollute the river, ocean and kills the wildlife, including the displacement of IPs and

communities.

Figure 2. Twenty years of the Philippine mining act.

Note. From IBON, 2015.

As a result of the logging and mining activities, the number of wildlife and species in our forest and ocean also continuously decline. These animals are important indicators of clean air, health forests and environment. The International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) had declared 418 animal species in the Philippines to be threatened - they are either vulnerable, endangered, or critically endangered, according to the IUCN red list criteria [29].

Figure 3. Fifty critically endangered species in the Philippines.

50 Critically Endangered Species in the Philippines

1. Philippine Eagle	11. Hawksbill Sea Turtle	21. Long Polyp Green	31. Green Turtle	41. Calamian Deer
2. Philippine Freshwater Crocodile	12. The Philippine Tarsier	22. False Flower Coral	32. Black Shama	42. Streak-breasted Bulbul
3. Tamaraw	13. Philippine Spotted Deer	23. Sei Whale	33. Panay Crateromys	43. Catanduanes Narrow-mouthed Frog
4. Walden's Hornbill	14. Sulu Hornbill	24. Blue Whale	34. Negros Shrew	44. Philippine Tube-nosed Fruit Bat
5. Visayan Warty Pig	15. Negros Fruit Dove	25. Fin Whale	35. Flame-templed Babbler	45. Luzon Peacock Swallowtail
6. Philippine Cockatoo	16. Flame-breasted Fruit Dove	26. Dinagat Hairy-tailed Rat	36. White-winged Flying Fox	46. Frog-faced Softshell Turtle
7. Negros Bleeding-heart	17. Giant Clams	27. Limbless Worm Skink	37. Mindoro Zone-tailed Pigeon	47. Tawitawi Brown Dove
8. Philippine Naked-backed Fruit Bat	18. Cebu Flowerpecker	28. Loggerhead Turtle	38. Japanese Night Heron	48. Mindoro Tree Frog
9. Philippine Forest Turtle	19. Golden-capped Fruit Bat	29. Dog-faced Water Snake	39. Apo Swallowtail	49. Hazel's Forest Frog
10. Dinagat Bushy-tailed Cloud Rat	20. Net Coral	30. Humphead Wrasse	40. Spiny Turtle	50. Mount Data Forest Frog

Note. From Owlcation, 2022.

According to DENR, there would be more plastics than fish by 2050, while oceans would be overheated and acidified if people fail to act now. While in plastic pollution, the country's annual generation of 17.5 billion tons of plastic waste estimates 20% of this waste ends up in the sea [30].

And because of the climate crisis brought about by day-to-day environment degradation, according to Climate Risk, a global knowledge portal at USAD, more than 17 provinces in the Philippines belong to the top 100 places in the world that will be affected by climate change [31].

Figure 4. Seventeen provinces in the Philippines among the global top 100

regions at risk to climate change.

Note. From XDI Gross Domestic Climate Risk, 2023.

X. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With our ecosystem's destruction, the Rights of Nature Ph bill, once it is passed, will be a powerful law that will now recognize ecosystems and natural communities have the right to exist and flourish. And by giving it legal personhood, it can now take a legal personhood in court.

To date, the pending bills for the "RIGHTS OF NATURE ACT" are the following: SB 143 Senator Risa Hontiveros, House of Representatives Senate, HB 7128 Congressman Joey Salceda NAPC, HB 7165 Congressman Arnan Panaligan, HB 7217 Congressman Edgar Chatto.

The Rights of Nature is also being included in the crafting of environment codes in some parts of the Philippines like Marinduque and Candon, Ilocos Sur. Environmental awareness and actions are growing and more people are now demanding the government to declare a climate emergency to save the ecosystems.

10.1 How the Rights of Nature Act aims to conserve the ecosystems

In an effort to protect the country's diverse ecosystems and rich biodiversity from continuous degradation and destruction, the Rights of Nature is being lobbied to different stakeholders. With the Rights of Nature bill, the destruction to the ecosystems to the following can be prevented, lessened, and hopefully stopped.

Protect the ecosystem of Sierra Madre which is threatened by the construction of Kaliwa Dam

The Rights of Nature movement has been helping and working with the

stakeholders in Infanta Quezon to stop the Kaliwa Dam through scientific research, legal advice, lobbying and educating the people about the importance of nature.

It was a victory when the rights of the Agos River the municipality of Infanta, Quezon, in the Philippines was recognized and filed as an ordinance. It was the first Rights of Nature recognition in the Philippines. Filed and championed by Vice-Mayor L.A. Ruanto of Infanta, Quezon, the ordinance establishes the Agos River as a Protected Area in the municipality, recognizing its rights. The people of Infanta, Quezon value the importance of natural resources like the Agos River and Sierra Madre and hope that this ordinance will help protect this ecosystem from corporations and companies that threaten to destroy it. It was filed last Nov 29, 2022, establishing the Agos River as a Protected Area in the Municipality of Infanta, Quezon recognizing its RIGHTS and appropriating funds thereof.

The people of Infanta, Quezon value the importance of their natural resources like the Agos River and Sierra Madre and hope that the Rights of Nature will be supported too by the neighboring municipalities.

The ordinance will also seek to protect the environment and other natural assets of Infanta from illegal activities from various corporations and companies that will threaten and destroy it. The Rights of Nature ordinance was filed in time of the town's commemoration of the 18th anniversary of the 2004 Flash Flood tragedy.

The Rights of Nature movement helped issue a TRO (temporary restraining order) to stop Sand Mining which has been destroying the ecosystem in Zambales-habitat of the critical Olive Ridley turtle & 'Sabalo.' Sand Mining has been destroying the ecosystem in Zambales particularly the Alusiis River and habitat of the critical Olive Ridley turtle.

Mining activities always have negative impacts on the environment - deforestation, erosion, contamination and alteration of soil profiles, contamination of local streams and wetlands, and cause air and water pollution. It also destroys watersheds and ancestral domains of Indigenous peoples.

The Rights of Nature Ph movement has been campaigning to end the termination of mining activities and has been helping the local communities in San Narciso, Zambales campaign against the illegal construction of the jetty port, dredging and sand mining. The ongoing construction activities at the shoreline has affected the Alusiis River—its water quality, ecosystem, health of the river and the condition of the coastal area. It is a sub-watershed, critical to the marine ecosystem and biodiversity of the province.

The Rights of Nature movement, through PMPI has been vocal about its support and has been capacitating the local communities in the struggle. RoN has been collaborating with them to provide a sustainable and regenerative management plan and strategies for the ecosystem.

The Rights of Nature Ph leads the campaign to declare climate emergency and calls the attention of the duty bearers to do their jobs in addressing the climate change and crisis.

The Rights of Nature Philippines (RoN PH) movement, steered by the Philippine Misereor Partnership Inc, Laudato Si Movement Pilipinas, Caritas Pilipinas, Conference of Major Superiors in the Philippines, and the Fellowship for the Care of Creation Association Inc., has compelled the duty-bearers to take immediate action to address the ongoing climate crisis. The declaration emphasized

the interconnectedness of all beings and our responsibility to protect and respect nature's inherent right to exist and flourish. Over 80 groups of local organizations, academe, IPs, parishes declared their support to RoN bill and calls on the government to declare climate emergency and provide immediate actions [32].

The Rights of nature campaign for the ecosystem of Pakil, Laguna's mountain and rivers to be protected from the threats of the construction of the Ahunan Hydropower.

The people of Pakil sought the help of the Rights of Nature movement to help campaign their opposition to the potential effects and impact of the proposed 1400MW Ahunan Pumped-Storage Hydropower Plant Project to Pakil, Laguna and its nearby municipalities.

The residents of Pakil are afraid that the letters of DENR administrative order, DAO 2017-15 on Public Participation is not followed to its intention as majority of the residents as stakeholders are not fully informed of the true scope of the project.

Pakil, the small, quaint but rich in culture and history in Laguna, blessed to be on the shores of Laguna Lake and the rugged mountains of Sierra Madre, is now threatened by the construction of the 1400MW Ahunan Pumped-Storage Hydropower Plant Project. They will be building a dam twice the size of the población area which will impact the lives of more than 12,000 in the municipality. The construction will denude the mountains, which is part of Sierra Madre, destroy the watershed, affect the quality of water, and impacts the extreme loss of biodiversity due to the construction.

The Rights of Nature Ph movement is now supporting the campaign through

lobbying and educating the stakeholders about the importance of their environment.

The Rights of Nature can give legal rights to the marine ecosystem and hold the people accountable for oil spill disasters

Last February 28, an environmental disaster and marine nightmare happened. A tanker spilled all its cargo oil estimated at around 800,000 liters of industrial fuel when it sank off the coast of Naujan, Oriental Mindoro. 5,185 hectares of corals, seagrass, and mangroves in Oriental Mindoro and Western Visayas are now damaged and it will take a minimum of 5 years to clean and start the rehabilitation.

Through the RoN Ph bill, it can hold the companies accountable and liable and make them pay for the rehabilitation of the affected marine ecosystem. This is also the opportunity that RoN campaigns the need to shift to renewable energy sources and gradual phase out our dependence on fossil fuels.

Rights of Nature is now acknowledged in the 30x30 plan to combat climate crisis

The High Ambition Coalition (HAC) for Nature and People is an intergovernmental group of more than 100 countries co-chaired by Costa Rica and France and by the United Kingdom as Ocean co-chair, championing a global deal for nature and people with the central goal of protecting at least 30 per cent of land and 30% of the ocean, globally, by 2030. The 30x30 target is a global target that aims to halt the accelerating loss of species and protect vital ecosystems that are the source of our economic security.

After four years of fraught negotiations, the deal pledges to secure 30 percent of the planet as a protected zone by 2030 and to stump up \$30 billion in yearly conservation aid for the developing world. Countries approved a historic deal to reverse decades of environmental destruction threatening the world's species and ecosystems at a marathon UN biodiversity summit early Monday [33].

This is a victory and acknowledgment that ecosystems must now be recognized and protected. And humans taking a bold step to recognize its dependence to nature.

Human Rights & Rights of Nature are interconnected

The survival of humans depends on healthy ecosystems, and so protection of nature's rights in turn, advances human rights and well-being.

As we face the ongoing climate crisis, the urgency of protecting our environment and its ecosystems is ever-growing. The RoN highlights the importance of recognizing the rights of nature as integral to the promotion and protection of human rights and make a shift in an anthropocentric view of rights.

Humans must begin to understand that we are never and will never be above nature. We are all interconnected and rely on each other to survive. And by recognizing and helping pass the Rights of Nature bill will strengthen human rights (right to clean air, water, to feel safe, access to food). We must keep in mind that a healthy environment is “one of the basic human rights.”

The Rights of Nature becomes a guide for Environment Code

The Rights of Nature now becomes a guide in the development and crafting

of the environment code. Marinduque continues to include the RoN framework in to the Marinduque's Environment Code. This is to protect the ecosystems and rivers in Marinduque and prevent the opening of mine sites again which killed the Boac river during the country's worst mining disaster that happened in Mogpog and Boac in 1997.

10.2 How the Rights of Nature Act is different from the existing environment laws

The Philippine legal system is a mixture of customary usage, Roman (civil law) and Anglo-American (common law) systems, and Islamic law. And the main sources of Philippine law are the Constitution, statutes, treaties and conventions, and judicial decisions.

The first environmental laws in the Philippines is the P.D. No. 1151 established on June 6, 1977 and declared the Philippine Environmental Policy. It was followed by the Philippine environment Code Presidential Decree No. 1152 – an act for the protection of the environment of a broad sense. Its provisions are divided into titles, the major part of them dealing with specific aspects of environment protection.

In 2015, the Philippines committed to the Global Agenda 2030 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These recognized the need for an institutional paradigm shift by combining results, people and processes, with their 17 goals and 169 targets.

The 2020 EPI ranked the Philippines at 111 with an Environmental Performance Index (EPI) score of 38.4 and a regional standing of 9. The Philippines'

EPI ranking over the past decade, dropped from 55th in 2006 to 114th in 2014, but recovered to rank 66 out of 180 countries in 2016. The Philippines' performance is poorer compared with Singapore and Malaysia but is consistently better than Indonesia and Vietnam.

Improvements occurred in ENR management particularly in the reduction of open and denuded forestlands as well as the management of key terrestrial and marine protected areas. This resulted in the improvement of critical habitats arresting the extinction of threatened flora and fauna. These accomplishments were facilitated by the implementation of key environmental laws and policies such as: (1) Executive Order 23 on the Moratorium on Logging in Natural Forest and Executive Order 26 on the Implementation of the National Greening Program; (2) National Integrated Protected Area System Act; (3) Wildlife Resources Conservation and Protection Act; (4) Amended Fisheries Code; and (5) other governance modality in establishing conservation areas such as the local conservation areas and indigenous community conserved areas. Slight improvements in environmental quality are noted but monitoring of environmental compliance remains weak [34].

The Philippines has several environmental laws that aim to protect, uphold and conserve the country's natural resources for the nation and generations to come. Without these laws, there would be no regulations concerning pollution, contamination, hunting, or even response to disasters. Environmental law works to protect land, air, water, and soil. Negligence of these laws results in various punishments like fines, community service, and in some extreme cases, jail time.

In the chart below, the difference and advantage of the Rights of Nature bill are compared and outlined. We can see here how the Rights of Nature Ph bill can add that extra layer of protection to our ecosystem.

Table 1. Writ of kalikasan vs. rights of nature bill.

WRIT OF KALIKASAN	RIGHTS OF NATURE BILL
<p>The Writ of Kalikasan is a remedy available to a natural or juridical person, entity authorized by law, people’s organization, non-governmental organization, or any public interest group Representation & Standing - Any Philippine resident may file an action to enforce the rights or obligations recognized under this Act on behalf of the natural ecosystem, population, or process 53 accredited by or registered with any government agency, on behalf of persons whose constitutional right to a balanced and healthful ecology is violated, or threatened with violation by an unlawful act or omission of a public official or employee, or private individual or entity, involving environmental damage of such magnitude as to prejudice the life, health or property of inhabitants in two or more cities or provinces.</p>	<p>Representation & Standing - Any Philippine resident may file an action to enforce the rights or obligations recognized under this Act on behalf of the natural ecosystem, population, or process concerned, which shall be the real party in-interest. Upon the filing of any such action, the Court shall issue an order which shall contain a brief description of the cause of action and the reliefs prayed for, requiring all interested parties to manifest their interest to intervene in the case within a reasonable amount of time from notice thereof.</p>
OTHER ENVIRONMENTAL LAWS	RIGHTS OF NATURE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Singular. Addresses particular environmental damages. ● Reactionary. Punishes the act after the damage has been done. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wholistic. Addresses ecological damages and protects ecosystems. ● Preventive. Prohibits acts that cause irreversible ecological

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human-centered. Protects individuals only. ● Anthropocentric legal standing. Petitioners/complainants need to be those directly affected 	<p>damage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nature-centered. Protects the environment, specifically the ecosystem itself. ● Person is allowed to file a case on behalf of the ecosystem being damaged.
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In Laudato Si, Pope Francis shared that the “The Bible has no place for a tyrannical anthropocentrism unconcerned for other creatures,” a direct refutation of the anthropocentric view that the earth exists only as resources for humans to use. Now is also the time to correct the notion that Christians incorrectly interpreted the Scriptures that our being created in God's image and given dominion over the earth justifies absolute domination over other creatures. According to Pope Francis, the exploitative readings of Genesis have “incorrectly interpreted” it and that it should be Nature is not purely an instrumental good; rather, humans are in a “relationship of mutual responsibility” with it. Hence the Laudato Si is not only politically influential but theologically revolutionary. The Rights of Nature Ph is being also steered by Caritas Pilipinas and PMPI Inc has been working closely with different prelatures around the country [38].

Environmental awareness in the Islamic law is also high as it is the duty of all Muslims to respect, nurture and care for the environment. The Quran says, “If you want to see me and feel my existence then look at nature. Look at the things I have created.” This means that you should not be disturbing the objects that worship God. “The Earth is green and beautiful, and Allah has appointed you his stewards over it. The whole Earth has been created a place of worship, pure and clean. Whoever

plants a tree and diligently looks after it until it matures and bears fruit is rewarded.” Corruption of all kinds, including environmental corruption, which includes industrial pollution, environmental damage, and reckless exploitation and mismanagement of natural resources are disliked by Allah [39].

The Rights of Nature concept that everything is inter-related is also adhered in Buddhism. Buddhists teach the idea of the inter-relatedness of everything. This means that humans depend on nature and nature depends on humans. Harming one part of this whole is the same as harming all of it. Therefore, if people learn to live simply and in harmony with the world, the whole of the environment will benefit. If a person has the right mindset, Buddhists believe that the actions they perform will be beneficial not just to themselves but to the whole world, including the environment. They believe that our actions affect the planet in a harmful way because we are selfish and we crave things.

There are several constitutional mandates and environmental policies that recognize the Rights of Nature in its context. However, it fails to be recognized, there is lack of political will to implement it or simply these laws are ignored.

The 1987 constitution, Article II Sec. 15. States that the state shall protect and promote the right to health of the people and instill health consciousness among them while Sec. 16. The State shall protect and advance the right of the people to a balanced and healthful ecology in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature. While the Presidential Decree no. 1151, the Government recognizes the right of the people to a healthful environment and it shall be the duty and responsibility of each individual to contribute to the preservation and enhancement of the Philippine environment. These laws recognize the importance of a healthy ecosystem as necessary to human rights.

The Philippine Clean Water Act of 2004 (Republic Act No. 9275) aims to protect the country's water bodies from pollution from land-based sources (industries and commercial establishments, agriculture and community/household activities). And included here is the Section 16 - Clean-Up Operations and Clean-up liability wherein any person who causes pollution in or pollutes water bodies in excess of the applicable and prevailing standards shall be responsible to contain, remove and clean-up [40]. This should be used to protect the ecosystem, like the recent Mindoro oil spill. Through Rights of Nature Ph, it will be easy to file a case for the company responsible for the oil spill.

Take for example the SLAPP suit – *Strategic lawsuit against public participation (SLAPP)*.—A legal action filed to harass, vex, exert undue pressure or stifle any legal recourse that any person, institution or the government has taken or may take in the enforcement of environmental laws, protection of the environment or assertion of environmental rights shall be treated as a SLAPP. It was filed against Earth Island Institute' Dolphin Safe Monitoring Project in the Philippines that monitored hundreds of tuna companies to ensure that these companies adhere to international standards for Dolphin Safe tuna and lead protests and campaigns to free dolphins and whales from corporate tanks.

Another case is the Boracay becoming a cesspool. Boracay reached this condition because the government and everyone failed to implement Clean Water Act, Clean Air Act, Solid Waste Act, including the correct carrying capacity of the island.

With the on-going plans to reclaim 20,000 hectares of the 199,000-hectare Manila Bay area, it is hoped that Manila Bay can be granted legal personality so that it can protect itself from the reclamation and effect on its biodiversity. In terms of

plastic pollution, to this date there is still no list yet on Non-Environmentally Acceptable Packaging as required by Solid Waste Act. Plastic pollution continues to threaten the rivers, ocean and land to be polluted.

10.3 How the Rights of Nature Act can provide a bigger layer of legal protection to the environment

What sets the Rights of Nature Ph bill now is that laws recognizing the Rights of Nature will now have the premise that ecosystems and natural communities have the right to exist and flourish. Through Rights of Nature, people, communities, and governments have the authority to defend those rights on behalf of ecosystems and natural communities. Communities that have enacted Rights of Nature laws are empowered to reject governmental actions permitting unwanted and damaging development which would violate these rights as proven in other countries like New Zealand through its Te Urewera Act – recognizing that a forest has the same legal rights as a citizen [41].

People within a community could now step “into the shoes” of a mountain, stream, or forest ecosystem, and advocate for the rights of those natural communities. It calls for a system of jurisprudence in which those ecosystems are actually “seen” in court.

10.4 How the Rights of Nature promotes sustainable lifestyle and e-mining to protect natural resources and ecosystems

Part of the framework that the Rights of Nature in the Philippines aims is the shift to practice a sustainable lifestyle or the “sapat lifestyle.” It espouses that people and communities should now innovate and embrace a way of living that is in harmony

with nature to help conserve the natural resources. The Sapat lifestyle is also inculcated in the Buddhists belief that people need to live simply and respect the cycle and balance in nature so everything can continue for future generations.

The Rights of Nature framework also discusses the possibility and advantage of shifting to e-mining or extractive mining where we can recover most of the metals contained in old electronic devices allowing them to be re-used. With this, we can reuse these materials and avoid having to destroy forests, oceans, and other ecosystems through the traditional methods of mining. If properly collected and recycled, e-mining can help reduce the need to open up new mining projects, thus reducing our impacts to our environment and ecosystem. It advocates for respect of Earth's natural systems and functions and recognizes that nature has rights.

XI. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

The Philippines is known for its rich biodiversity and natural resources, but because of the continuous degradation to the environment like mining, logging, pollution and threat of humans to ecosystems, failure of existing environmental laws to protect nature, traditional and anthropocentric approaches, there is a strong need to adapt and use a new more eco-centric approach that can provide a new and more accountable, wholistic environmental protection.

With all the destruction happening, with the climate crisis intensifying, all points to one as the source of all environmental degradation– and that is us humans. We need to change our mindset that we own everything in this planet, that we are above in the food chain, at the apex of the web of life. We need to stop thinking that nature was placed here on earth to serve, feed, protect human. All of these anthropocentric thinking must stop if we want our future children to still have a safe home in the future.

There is now a need to recognize the Rights of Nature framework as an immediate solution to environmental degradation. Recognizing the rights of nature can help ensure the protection and conservation of these resources for future generations. Overall, adapting the rights of nature in the Philippines is a promising step towards promoting environmental protection and sustainability. It is important to ensure that such measures are implemented effectively and are backed by strong legal frameworks to ensure their success.

The Rights of Nature Ph bill if passed can also help address the devastating impact of climate change. It can make governments and corporations more responsible and accountable when dealing with nature. And think twice before they

dump their waste in the ocean, extract a mountain, poison the river and kill trees and forests. The RoN Ph bill can help safeguard ecosystems and other living species.

The proposed Rights of Nature Act will now protect all ecosystems by giving it a legal personality to natural ecosystems and processes, including all of their living and non-living elements, as well as any distinct and identifiable portions, aggregations or components thereof, shall be recognized under law. Any person who violates any of the provisions of this Act or its Implementing Rules and Regulations shall, upon conviction by final judgment, be punished by imprisonment of not less than six (6) months nor more than two (2) years or a fine of not less than Five Million pesos (PhP5,000,000), nor more than Ten Million pesos (PhP10,000,000), or both, at the discretion of the court. The crime of ecological destruction shall be punished by reclusion perpetua as well as a fine in the amount of not less than ten million pesos (P10,000,000.00), or the cost of the actual damage caused to the natural ecosystem or process concerned, whichever is higher.

A conservation committee will be set up to handle the trust fund and implement the measures necessary for protection, preservation, restoration, or renewal of the natural ecosystem. In case of SLAPP, the defendant in a SLAPP may file a special motion to dismiss at any point of the proceedings alleging that the case is a SLAPP.

In case the offender is a public official or employee, the penalty of removal from office, with perpetual disqualification shall likewise be imposed. In case the offender is an official or employee of any Government-owned or controlled corporation (GOCC), the penalty of dismissal from employment shall be imposed with perpetual disqualification from serving in any GOCC or public office.

To date, the Rights of Nature movement here in the Philippines is only 5 years

but because the framework has made it very clear for all its advocates and audience that without nature, we are nothing, and that all living entities should have intrinsic rights to exist, the RoN Ph movement grows even more stronger and louder with the objective of stopping environment destruction and start regenerating all that was lost. The current Philippine laws on the environment are human-centered, it focuses on protecting the environmental rights of individuals but not of the environment itself. With the RON bill, it now presents a different perspective: nature gets legal protection because it's recognized as a distinct legal entity that deserves legal representation.

Lastly, the beauty and strength of the Rights of Nature framework is that it also reminds us to be humble, to recognize all living things have a right to life because that is the purpose of all things created – to exist and to flourish. More so, when we say that we are connected with nature, it can still be viewed as an emotional and empathic relationship with the rest of the natural world and a perception of interdependence. And the connection with nature has been well explored in the fields of psychology, sociology and environmental education and in political and philosophical literature.

Lastly, as a nation that is predominantly Catholic and with a strong faith in God, the Pope also reminds us that Nature cannot be regarded as something separate from ourselves, we are part of nature, we are nature.

The Rights of Nature Ph bill is our hope to protect and restore our ecosystems for humans to have a chance of existence in the future.

XII. REFERENCES

- [1] UN Org. (2023). Rights of Nature: A Catalyst for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Agenda on Water. UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs Sustainable Development. <https://sdgs.un.org/partnerships/rights-nature-catalyst-implementation-sustainable-development-agenda-water#>
- [2] Philippine Star. (2018). Kaliwa Dam will destroy Sierra Madre biodiversity. <https://www.philstar.com/business/science-and-environment/2018/11/29/1872521/kaliwa-dam-will-destroy-sierra-madre-biodiversity>
- [2] Inquirer.net. (2017). Study: World pollution deadlier than wars, disasters, hunger. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/939414/study-world-pollution-deadlier-than-wars-disasters-hunger>
- [3] Ecosystem. (2021). Ecosystem definition. <https://www.biologyonline.com/dictionary/ecosystem>.
- [4] Ecosystem. (2023). Key Biodiversity Areas. <http://www.philchm.ph/key-biodiversity-areas/>
- [5] Environment and Ecology. (2017). Environmental problems. <http://environment-ecology.com/environment-writings/839-15-major-current-environmental-problems.html>
- [6] GreenDev Solutions. (2018). Philippine Environment Laws. <https://greendevsolutions.com/environmental-laws-and-policies-in-the-philippines/>
- [7] Earth Law Center. (2017). Rights of Nature at the International Level. <https://www.earthlawcenter.org/blog-entries/2017/10/rights-of-nature-within-the-un-and-iucn>
- [8] UN.(2022).UN conference concludes with 'historic' deal to protect a third of the

world's biodiversity. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/12/1131837>

[9] ReliefWeb. (2022). Philippines: Country Climate and Development Report 2022. <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/philippines-country-climate-and-development-report-2022>

[10] Senate.gov.ph. (2016). S. BN 143. <http://legacy.senate.gov.ph/lisdata/3785134292!.pdf>

[11] Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights. (2019). Faith Communities and the Rights of Nature. <https://www.centerforenvironmentalrights.org/faith-rights-of-nature>

[12] Fitzner, Zach. (2019). The Philippines may be the next nation to grant rights to nature. <https://www.earth.com/news/non-human-nature-rights/>

[13] Invisible Hand Film. (2017). What Are Rights of Nature? <https://www.invisiblehandfilm.com/what-are-rights-of-nature>

[14] CELF. (2022). Rights of Nature: A timeline. <https://celf.org/rights-of-nature/timeline/>

[15.1] Bresler, Alex. (2020). 7 Countries That Have Legally Recognized the Rights of Nature. <https://matadornetwork.com/read/countries-legally-recognized-rights-nature/>

[15.2] CRIN Org. (1994). Minors Oposa v. Secretary of the Department of Environmental and Natural Resources. <https://archive.crin.org/en/library/legal-database/minors-oposa-v-secretary-department-environmental-and-natural-resources.html>

[16] Rights of Nature PH. (2019). Introducing the Rights of Nature Campaign. <https://rightsofnature.org.ph/what-is-right-of-nature-ph/>

[17] Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights. (2019). Rights of Nature: Theory, Law, and Emerging Jurisprudence Legal Training.

<https://www.centerforenvironmentalrights.org/rights-of-nature-legal-training>

[18] Center for Democratic and Environmental Rights. (2019). The Philippines is leading Southeast Asia in advancing protections for the rights of nature.

<https://www.centerforenvironmentalrights.org/where-we-work/philippines>

[19] Roxburgh, Katy. (2022). The High Ambition Coalition for Nature and People Formalizes Partnership with the Campaign for Nature To Deliver 30 by 30 Goal.

<https://www.campaignfornature.org/hac-and-cfn-formalize-partnership>

[20] Global Witness. (2022). “Nature-based solutions”: using digital methods to investigate corporate greenwashing. <https://www.globalwitness.org/en/campaigns/greenwashing/using-digital-methods-to-investigate-corporate-greenwashing/>

[21] Earth Law Center. (2018). Seeds of Hope for Earth Law in the Philippines.

<https://www.earthlawcenter.org/blog-entries/2018/9/seeds-of-hope-for-earth-law-in-the-philippines>

[22] Boyd, Elizabeth. (2020). Considering Environmental / Property Law Towards a More Eco-Centric Position Within Legal Education. <https://www.learning.law.cuhk.edu.hk/post/considering-environmental-property-law-towards-a-more-eco-centric-position-within-legal-education>

[23] Global Witness. (2022). Missing: Environmental and human rights policies notably absent from Ferdinand Marcos Jr.’s first state of nation address. <https://www.globalwitness.org/en/blog/environmental-human-rights-policies-ferdinand-marcos-jrs-state-of-nation-address/>

[24] Shannon. (2015). What’s the difference between regeneration and restoration? <https://regenesisgroup.com/regeneration-vs-restoration>

[25] Soil Association. (2019). A ten year transition.

<https://www.soilassociation.org/causes-campaigns/a-ten-year-transition-to-agroecology>

[26] CNN. (2022). PH remains worst place for land and environmental defenders. <https://www.cnnphilippines.com/news/2022/9/30/PH-remains-worst-place-for-land-and-environmental-defenders-in-Asia.html>

[27] Sandhu. (2021). Environmental Governance in the Philippines. https://ncpag.upd.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/SANDHU_Environmental-Governance_09242021.pdf

[28] Michaelson, Jay. (2015). Pope Francis' environmental encyclical is even more radical than it appears. <https://religionnews.com/2015/06/19/pope-francis-environmental-encyclical-even-radical-appears-commentary/>

[29] Siasat. (2022). Conserving environment is every Muslims responsibility. <https://www.siasat.com/conserving-environment-is-every-muslims-responsibility-the-quran-says-so/>

[30] Earth Law Center. (2017). Rights of Nature at the International Level. <https://www.earthlawcenter.org/blog-entries/2017/10/rights-of-nature-within-the-un-and-iucn>

[31] Official Gazette. (2001). Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/constitutions/the-1987-constitution-of-the-republic-of-the-philippines/the-1987-constitution-of-the-republic-of-the-philippines-article-ii/>

[32] Official Gazette. (1979). Philippine Environmental Policy. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1977/06/06/presidential-decree-no-1151-s-1977/>

[33] EMB. (2021). Philippine Clean Water Act. <https://r12.emb.gov.ph/ra-9275-the-philippine-clean-water-act>

[34] Preda. (2000). Writ of Kalikasan, Amparo, Habeas Corpus.

<https://www.preda.org/2012/writ-of-kalikasan-amparo-habeas-corpus/>

[35] Project Jurisprudence. (2019). Writ of Kalikasan continuing mandamus.

<https://www.projectjurisprudence.com/2019/12/writ-of-kalikasan-vs-writ-of-continuing-mandamus>

[36] Palmer, Mark. (2019). Earth Island Philippines Fights SLAPP Suit Over Anti-Captivity. <https://savedolphins.eii.org/news/earth-island-philippines-fights-slapp-suit-over-anti-captivity>

[37] Earthlaws. (2014). New Zealand – legal rights for forests and rivers. <https://www.earthlaws.org.au/aclc/rights-of-nature/new-zealand/>

[38] IJC. (2019). What do we mean when we say that nature has rights? <https://www.ijc.org/system/files/commentfiles/2019-10-Nicolette%20Slagle/FAQ.pdf>

[39] Shannon. (2015). What's the difference between regeneration and restoration? <https://regenesishgroup.com/regeneration-vs-restoration>

[40] Cryer, Paul. (2017). Why ecocentrism is the key pathway to sustainability. <https://mahb.stanford.edu/blog/statement-ecocentrism/>

[41] Howe, Helen. (2017). Making Wild Law Work—The Role of 'Connection with Nature' and Education in Developing an Ecocentric Property Law. <https://academic.oup.com/jel/article/29/1/19/2585049>

[42] Digal, Santosh. (2023). Catholic environmentalists call on the Philippine Congress to recognise the rights of nature. <https://www.asianews.it/news-en/Catholic-environmentalists-call-on-the-Philippine-Congress-to-recognise-the-rights-of-nature-58046.html>

[43] Cullinan, Cormac. (2003). Wild Law: A Manifesto for Earth Justice. <https://philpapers.org/rec/CULWLA>

[44] Burdon, Peter. (2011). Earth Jurisprudence: Private Property and the

environment.

[45] Wood, MaryChristina. (2014). Nature's Trust: Environmental Law for a New Ecological Age

[46] Boyd, David. (2017). The Rights of Nature: A Legal Revolution That Could Save the World. <https://www.environmentandsociety.org/mml/interview-david-r-boyd-author-rights-nature-legal-revolution-could-save-world>

[47] Berder, Sharon. (2020). Ecological Governance: Reappraising Law's Role in Protecting Ecosystem Functionality. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/transnational-environmental-law/article/abs/ecological-governance-reappraising-laws-role-in-protecting-ecosystem-functionality-by-olivia-woolley-cambridge-university-press-2014-261-pp-65-hb-isbn-9781107060456/727423B24E32DA7110B3B6D71B5935E3>

ANNEX A (INTERVIEWS)

As part of the research, an interview was conducted with the Dumagat-Remontados who participated in the No to Kaliwa Dam march.

“Maraming sakunang dadating nasa amin kapag sinira ninyo ang Sierra Madre tulad ng bagyo, baha.”

Alfredo dela Cruz
Dumagat-Remontados

“Ilulubog nito ang kultura, mahal namin sa buhay. Mababaon na sila sa ilalim ng tubig...hindi na naming makikita.”Turo ko sa mga anak ko ang kalikasan ay hindi sa atin, kaya wag natin sisirain.”

Nanay

“Ayaw ko masira ang kalikasan dahil dito ko kinukuha kabuhayan ko.”

Rudy
Dumagat-Remontados

“Pinagaaway kami, magsisimula nanaman itong tribal war”

Aling Elsie
Dumagat-Remontados

“Ang sierra madre ang pangalawang nanay ko, siya ang nature sa akin ng lahat ng kaalaman ko, nag-aalaga sakin, bumubuhay at nagmamahal sa akin.”

JanCarlo
Dumagat-Remontados

An interview was conducted with the following respondents and stakeholders in Zambales.

“Hindi naming pinagdadamot, kasi walang mayari ng kalikasan, para po sa lahat. Walang turo turo.”

Gian Quiambao
Youth

“Gusto ko maganda ang dagat para sa apo ko. Kung hindi naming paglaban ang karapatan ng kalikasan, paano ang magiging anak namin?”

Arlynde Ala
Bangus Fry Catcher Association

“Kahit nakikita nila ung ginagawa samin, hindi nila dindesisyunan kahit alam nilang legal, dapat masosolve na yan sabagay, baka sabagay hindi naiintindihan or baka tinatago ng barangay kung ano talaga karapatan namin.”

Sherilyn Magtanong
Bangus Fry Catcher Association

“Ayaw ko na magvolunteer, kasi walang suporta galing sa LGU, boluntaryo lahat. Bantay dagat na walang suporta, bantay salakay na walang sahod, ayoko na.”

Jose B. Placido
Sto.Nino Fish Landing Association, Bantay Dagat

“Nang mag camp kami, tinawag kaming pulang araw, bendeta, hindi kami makaakyat sa barangay, ang iniisip nila bayaran kami, lumalaban daw kami kasi bayaran kami, pero hindi kami bayaran talaga lang ayaw naming pagalawung community kasi dyan kami kumukuha ng pagkain, pang-aral etc. Pati ung mga members ng fisherfolk tinanggal, fisher nalang daw, tapos hindi na din kami binibigyan ng indigency and pati ayuda, dun na lang daw kami humingi sa nagorganize sa camp. Ayaw nila kami bigyan ng ayuda kasi lumaban kami, sana magbago ang sitwasyon namin.”

Jellen Adarayon
Bangus Fryer President

During the first National Conference on sustainable agriculture, the following interview was conducted with an IP participant about their relationship with nature.

“Paano tayo magkakaroon ng food security, lagi ninyo pinapayagan ninyo putulin ang mga puno sa gubat?”

Tubag Jugatan
Pamayanan ng Lakas
Aeta from Zambales

ANNEX B (PHOTOS)

Note. From *Groups push for stronger legal protection for the environment*, by D. Cruz, 2019, Rappler (<https://www.rappler.com/moveph/235969-environmental-advocates-groups-push-rights-nature-bill/>).

Green groups welcome Philippine 'rights of nature' bill

Church and pro-environment groups describe the filing of the proposed measure as 'historic'

Note. From *Green groups welcome Philippine 'rights of nature' bill*, by M. Saludes, 2019, UCA News (<https://www.ucanews.com/news/green-groups-welcome-philippine-rights-of-nature-bill/86254>).

Note. From Conference on Rights and Dignity for ALL, by PMPI, 2023, PMPI (<https://www.facebook.com/media/set/?set=a.6822789271070891&type=3>).

Note. From Celebrating 10 Years of Rights of Nature in Ecuador, by The Global Alliance for the Rights of Nature, 2018, The Pachamama Alliance (<https://news.pachamama.org/celebrating-10-years-of-rights-of-nature-in-ecuador>).

Note. From *On Earth Day, Philippine gov't urged to prioritize protection vs climate crisis*, by J. Torres Jr., 2021, LICAS.NEWS (<https://philippines.licas.news/2021/04/22/on-earth-day-philippine-govt-urged-to-prioritize-protection-vs-climate-crisis/>).

Note. From *Highest salute to our RoN Champions*, by PMPI, 2023, PMPI (<https://www.facebook.com/rightsofnatureph/photos/pb.100064943280193.-2207520000/3300787170185466/?type=3>).

Personal communication, Interview about Kaliwa Dam (own photo, 2023).

Note. From *Zambales environmentalists protest causeway, jetty projects*, by J. Manabat, 2021, Rappler (<https://www.rappler.com/nation/zambales-environmentalists-protest-causeway-jetty-projects/>).

Note. From Rights of Nature PH Declares Climate Emergency, Pushes for Passage of Rights of Nature Bill by Pressenza, 2023, Pressenza (<https://www.pressenza.com/2023/03/rights-of-nature-ph-declares-climate-emergency-pushes-for-passage-of-rights-of-nature-bill/>).

Pakil residents protest construction of hydropower plant

Bulatlat Contributors © September 7, 2022 ahunan hydropower project, hydropower plants

Note. From Pakil residents protest construction of hydropower plant by Bulatlat Contributors, 2022, Bulatlat (<https://www.bulatlat.com/2022/09/07/pakil-residents-protest-construction-of-hydropower-plant/>).

This photo from the Philippine Coast Guard shows the oil spill that followed the sinking of MT Princess Empress in waters off Naujan town in Oriental Mindoro province early Tuesday morning, February 28, 2023. PCG photo

Note. From PCG: Oil tanker off Oriental Mindoro now fully submerged, oil spill worsens by J. E. Mendoza, 2023, Inquirer.net (<https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1736955/pcg-oil-tanker-off-oriental-mindoro-now-fully-submerged-oil-spill-worsens>).

Nearly Every Country Signs On to a Sweeping Deal to Protect Nature

Roughly 190 nations, aiming to halt a dangerous decline in biodiversity, agreed to preserve 30 percent of the planet's land and seas. The United States is not officially a participant.

Note. From Nearly Every Country Signs On to a Sweeping Deal to Protect Nature, by C. Einhorn, 2022, The New York Times (<https://www.nytimes.com/2022/12/19/climate/biodiversity-cop15-montreal-30x30.html>).

Note. From *The Rights of Nature PH is a growing civil society movement advocating for a change in human relationships with nature by PMPI, 2022, PMPI* (<https://www.facebook.com/rightsofnatureph/photos/pb.100064943280193.-2207520000/3133381980259320/?type=3>).

ANGELES REPORT

'TRAINING/WORKSHOP ON THE REVIEW, UPDATING, AND IMPROVEMENT OF THE MARINDUQUE ENVIRONMENTAL CODE'

Kasalukuyang isinasagawa ang ikalawang araw ng Training/Workshop on the Review, Updating & Improvement of the Marinduque Environmental Code na nagsimula noong Nobyembre 28, 2022 sa Capt. Rolando dela Rosa Events Place, Bangbangalon, Boac, Marinduque.

Ang nasabing training/workshop ay pinangungunahan ng Committee of the Whole na pinamunuan ni Vice Governor Adeline M. Angeles at dinaluhan ng mga kinatawan mula sa iba't-ibang tanggapan mula sa pamahalaang (local at national level) kabilang ang Civil Society Organization (CSO).

Isang Team mula sa Philippine Misereor Partnership Inc. (PMPI) na pinangunahan ni Atty. Mario Maderazo at Mrs. Yolanda Esguerra na tumulong bilang Resource person at facilitator.

NOVEMBER 29, 2022

Note. From *Workshop on the Review, Updating and Improvement of the Marinduque Environmental Code by MACEC, 2022.*

Note. From *The Philippines makes history by recognizing the rights of the Agos River* by Global Alliance for the Rights of Nature, 2022, GARN (<https://www.instagram.com/garnglobal/>).

Note. From *Do You Hear the Cry of the Poor? Mercy Global Action's Participation in Laudato Si' Week* by Mercy International Association, 2020, Mercy International Association (<https://www.mercyworld.org/newsroom/do-you-hear-the-cry-of-the-poor-mercy-global-action-participation-in-laudato-si-week/>).

Diagram 'Ego-Eco'-Humankind is part of the ecosystem, not apart from or above it. This diagram depicts this simple fact clearly (diagram: S. Lehmann, 2010).

Note. From *Ego Vs. Eco – Where Is Bushcraft?* by Nature Outside, 2015, Nature Outside (<https://www.natureoutside.com/ego-vs-eco-where-is-bushcraft/>).